

concept

D6.1- Data Management Plan (DMP)

30/06/2024

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D6.1 DATA MANAGEMENT PLAN (DMP)

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Abstract	This document summarizes the data management strategy of the project. The document is living and will be continuously updated during the project.

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This document provides information about the Data Management Plan (DMP) of the CONCEPT consortium. It provides general rules on data collection and curation, and how CONCEPT adheres to the Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability and Reusability (FAIR) guidelines of the Horizon Europe program. The document is living, and will be updated and versioned during and as part of the project progress.

1 DATA SUMMARY

This data management plan (DMP) describes how data generated during the CONCEPT project by the project consortium members will be collected, managed, curated and appropriately shared. In Project data will generally refer to any equipment or simulation measurement or output, including those intended for tabular presentation, graphical presentation or as images (e.g. microscopy). These data will be collected in different experiments and simulations and referenced to samples used in the project and their characterization, which will be in digital format.

1.1 PURPOSE OF THE DATA COLLECTION

The main project objective is to develop materials systems and proof-of-concept devices for next-generation information and communication technologies (ICT), in particular ferroelectric computing- and memory devices as well as photonic integrated circuits. The project also aims to increase the technology readiness level of these types of device systems and bring them closer to market. All data collection and processing has as its sole purpose the fulfilment of the main project objectives described above.

1.2 RELATION TO THE OBJECTIVES OF THE PROJECT

The data collection and processing is directly relevant to the goals of the constituent work packages in the corresponding Description of Action (DoA), which have as their sole purpose the fulfilment of the main project objective described above.

1.3 TYPES AND FORMATS OF DATA GENERATED/COLLECTED

The data to be generated/collected during this project will come from four principal sources: (1) Simulation, e.g. atomistic density functional theory (DFT) and Monte Carlo simulations, (2) Technical drawings and models, e.g. CAD-drawings, (3) Raw data from laboratory (experimental) work, e.g. from X-ray- and electron based techniques and synthesis development, and (4) Processed data, e.g. output from data treatment software, e.g. Origin Pro and Excel. A list of pertinent data types will be curated as part of the DMP as the project progresses, updated in a shared project folder, and periodically updated in a table in the DMP

All data types will, as a general rule, be paired with a comprehensive set of explanatory notes (README files), documenting the constituent data and metadata in the form of plain and accessible text files.

In addition to time stamped computer files, laboratory work is also documented in standard hand-written and signed lab journals. These are in principle not openly accessible, but scans and copies can be made when needed and by reasonable request.

1.4 RE-USE OF EXISTING DATA

Some of the input for simulation is based on existing molecular structure- and crystal structure data. These data are already available in open-access data repositories and their re-use will be clearly and transparently documented.

Some of the input for materials synthesis are based on existing process data. Most, but not all of this data is openly available in scientific journals. Whenever openly available data is reused, this will be clearly and transparently documented. Whenever non-disclosed process data is reused, this will either be published as part of the new data, or otherwise clearly and transparently documented. Whenever protected data is reused, this will be clearly documented.

1.5 ORIGIN OF THE DATA

All simulation data (data type 1) will be generated by CONCEPT project participants in the relevant areas described in the DoA, on either local computers at the partner institutions or on national and European computer clusters.

Technical drawings and models (data type 2) will be generated by the CONCEPT project participants as vector drawings from CAD-based software.

Raw data from experimental work (data type 3) will be generated by the CONCEPT project participants in their respective participating laboratories or at large-infrastructure centers such as synchrotron facilities. These experimental data will be derived from samples synthesized or devices constructed by CONCEPT project scientists during the lifetime of the project.

Processed data (data type 4) will be generated by CONCEPT project participants at their respective participating laboratories, at large-infrastructure centers such as synchrotron facilities, or at external locations during seminars or workshops.

1.6 EXPECTED SIZE OF THE DATA

A preliminary estimate of the expected size of the data is in the 1 – 10 TB range. The largest components of the data will come from atomistic simulations and animations, image files from data characterization (from participant laboratories or large infrastructure) and image files from processed data. Other data is expected to require less than 100 GB in total.

1.7 DATA UTILITY: TO WHOM IT WILL BE USEFUL

The scientific results and their associated data will be of general interest to the scientific community, and to the public at large, depending on the nature of these results. The simulation data, technical drawings and raw characterization data will be of interest to the materials science community working in similar areas. The processed data will be of interest to the wider scientific community.

2 FAIR

This section outlines the strategy for adhering to the Horizon Europe Programme’s “Guidelines on FAIR data management”.

2.1 MAKING DATA FINDABLE, INCLUDING PROVISIONS FOR METADATA

All of the data from each four data types enumerated in Section 1.3 will be, as the preferred option, posted to domain-specific and open-access data repositories upon publication of the results. The use of domain-specific open-access repositories increases the visibility of data (making it more ‘findable’) to those communities who are most likely to seek and re-use it.

For materials science, raw data, such as x-ray diffraction spectra, can be made accessible through *Materials Cloud*, or more curated in the form of preprints on arXiv where raw data can be included in a machine readable format. Atomistic simulation data can be made available through the NoMaD repository (www.nomad-coe.eu), which adheres to FAIR principles. In cases where domain-specific repositories are not available, CONCEPT will store these in a locally curated cloud system with open access to the community or through a repository such as Zenodo. This will then be linked to on the project webpage to increase the visibility and ease of access.

In all cases (irrespective of specific data repository or locally curated cloud), all data contributions will be identified with a unique and persistent DOI that will be published together with its associated open-access, peer-reviewed scientific publication. Links to the data and identifying DOI will be posted openly available on the CONCEPT webpages (<https://conceptproject.eu/>). The open access publications, linked data in the

public data repositories and the CONCEPT project website will also use the same system of specific keywords to enable the data to be easily found. The naming convention for each data set will be directly associated with the corresponding peer-reviewed scientific publication so that the latter can be easily identified from the former.

The metadata associated with the four data types are quite variable. Most pertinent is the metadata related to experimental conditions for laboratory work (type 2), and software codes (type 1). Metadata on collected characterization raw data is also important and will be made publicly available. In all cases, metadata findability will be increased by adding an explanatory README text file, to fully document the data and metadata included in the contribution. We will make sure to include a change log to explicitly document any changes made between versions.

All partners will adhere to a standard file naming convention to increase findability. Per June 26, this is *initials_runningnumber_material_runningnumber*. Whenever posted to data repositories, a README text file will always follow the data to explain the naming convention.

2.2 MAKING DATA OPENLY ACCESSIBLE

All data generated during the CONCEPT project will be made openly available upon completion of the peer-review process associated with each constituent study and after any intellectual property has been identified (*as open as possible, as closed as necessary*) and steps taken to protect this. During the peer-review processes we may also post provisional results (indicated as actively undergoing peer-review) to local open-access cloud systems or a preprint server, such as arXiv or Chemrxiv. Primary data will, as a ground rule, **not** be made publicly available before the peer-reviewed publishing process is completed, or as part of the peer-review process unless absolutely necessary for proper review of a scientific publication.

Whenever posted, each data contribution will include an explanatory text (README) that will clearly and completely describe the metadata associated with the dataset, as well as any tools or methods needed to access and process the data. For the bulk of the data the tools needed to visualize and analyze the data are freely available through open-source software. Whenever this is not the case, the associated README file will explicitly state the conditions of the analysis and tools that have been used. The goal is that the users can fully and dynamically repeat and reproduce the analytical and/or computational steps conducted on the data provided.

2.3 MAKING DATA INTEROPERABLE

All datasets will be provided in open and standard machine-readable data formats (e.g. .csv, .pdf, .txt), whenever possible. When raw data is not available in such formats, CONCEPT project members will strive to transfer the data to such data formats, together with the original native data format. In the rare cases that this is also not possible, e.g. through a proprietary data format, the associated README text file will explicitly state this and the conditions for which the raw data can be acquired and opened will be described. This includes data of all datatypes, including any associated metadata.

2.4 INCREASE DATA RE-USE (THROUGH CLARIFYING LICENSES)

As a ground rule, data generated during the CONCEPT project will be made publicly available with a Creative Commons attribution license (CC-by), allowing all users to share and adapt the material for any purpose, but under the terms that proper and complete attribution to the original materials be made, and that any changes to the materials be specified. This licensing permits the widest possible reuse of the data generated while still requiring that the original work (and its support by Horizon Europe) be acknowledged. No embargo period will be imposed on any of the data of this kind once it is released, following completion of the peer-review process.

As noted above, datasets will be provided in open and standard data formats (e.g. .csv, .pdf, .txt), whenever possible, to ensure ease of access, long-term usability and preservation of the data.

The data generated during the CONCEPT project will be publicly available for as long as the data repositories themselves remain available (>10 years).

3 ALLOCATION OF RESOURCES

All of the open data repositories to be used during the CONCEPT project provide free-hosting for the volumes of data that we expect to generate during the CONCEPT project – and in principle this free-hosting is “indefinite”. Thus, we do not anticipate any costs associated with the posting or hosting of data to these repositories. This also includes locally curated cloud-based storage. We do, however, anticipate to have costs associated with publishing the associated open-access scientific articles (article publishing costs, APC’s), which we have already budgeted in the CONCEPT project costs. We anticipate the bulk of APCs will be covered by institutional or jurisdictional agreements with publishers or by publishing in Diamond open access venues.

All the data management responsibilities lie with the project manager (Henrik H. Sønsteby), but all partners are required to adhere to the DMP and curate their own data.

Because all the data generated by the CONCEPT project will be posted to public data repositories or locally curated clouds which do not charge hosting costs, there are no foreseen costs related to the long term preservation of data generated in CONCEPT.

4 DATA SECURITY

All experimental raw- and treated data generated during the CONCEPT project will be securely and redundantly stored. This includes copies to secondary storage whenever data is created, and medium-term storage on cloud-servers provided by the CONCEPT partner institutions. Local data curation, storage and back-up policies at each partner will ensure security and availability of the project data.

In all cases, following peer-review, these data will be permanently archived and versioned on open-access data repositories or locally curated open-access cloud-servers.

5 ETHICAL ASPECTS

We have identified no ethical issues with the data generated in the project, including collection, generation or actual content. This is also stated in the DoA.

6 OTHER

The following describes some additional aspects of the DMP, as well as some exceptions to the general data management.

6.1 THE CONCEPT DMP AS A LIVING DOCUMENT

The CONCEPT DMP is a living document that will be revised and updated as the project progresses. The DMP will be versioned and any changes will be explicitly stated in the revision history.

6.2 EXCEPTIONS TO THE CONCEPT DMP

Some partners, particularly SME's or large industry, curate business sensitive data that will not be made publicly available. We have identified the following exceptions as of June 25, 2024:

1. **Baldur Coatings AS.** Some CAD drawings of reactor design will be made openly available with reference to Baldur Coatings AS. The reactor design on a detailed level and the reports related to its construction will not be made openly available due to business sensitivity. Some of the CAD drawings can be reused and usable by third parties in the extent that it might be included on the CONCEPT websites and future potential articles and reports from the CONCEPT website, but the reports and work sketches are not intended for the public.
2. **Lumiphase AG.** Full measurement data of films grown by molecular beam epitaxy as well as processing parameters will be kept confidential, since they are for a commercial product in a competitive landscape, where competitors of Lumiphase would gain an advantage.
3. **IBM Research.** Data produced on business sensitive materials and devices, including metadata, will not be made publicly available.
4. **Volatec Oy.** Data produced on business sensitive materials and chemicals, including metadata, will not be made publicly available.